

Social Status of Women

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“ I measure the progress of community by the degree of progress Which women have achieve”

- Dr.B.R.Ambedkar.

Introduction

Every Society has its natural thing both man and woman on equal lines, as human beings. Unfortunately, in that society the relations between men and women are not equal. Men are considered in social, economic and political as dominated and strong where women are considered as weak and dependent to their opposite sex. History of mankind says that in ancient period, women had enjoyed equal status and prestige on par with men in all walks of life. In medieval period, throughout the word, religion dominated the state, and subjugated the women to men and religion. In modern period, with the advancement of education in many parts of the world, women started to obtain their lost status through the various kinds of activities.

Women, in Indian society have had the experience from the very outset. Earlier times, women had the honorable and respectable position in the Rig Vedic period, they enjoyed the liberty, equality in social, economic and political life on par with men. Women used to control the family and worked for their families’ welfare. The society had experience with matriarchal families Rahul Sankrutyayan in his book *Olga to Ganga* and the African Writer Jomo Kenyatta in his *Facing Mount Kenya* referred to the matriarchal families. They advocated that in the days of matriarchal families. Women were physically stronger than men. Menstruation, Pregnancy and child birth have reduced the physical strength of women and at that time she had to depend on men for food, care a protection. This led to the change of matriarchal families changed to patriarchal families. Polygamy was introduced later. But it has been remarked that, women enjoyed a high respectable place in society and family.1

1. Fall of Women in Later Vedic Period

The position enjoyed by women in the Rig Vedic period deteriorated in the later Vedic civilization. It is examined that a daughter began to be regarded as a curse. Women were denied the

right of inheritance and ownership of property. Even husbands and sons became the owners of women's earnings². After the Vedic period, the position of women went worst day by day, during the later Vedic period, Manu Smriti was written and came into force and it degraded women in all walks of life as follows:

1. Education:

' Women have no right to study Vedas.... Women cannot utter the Veda they are as unclean as untruth is.'

nu : - IX – 18.

2. Marriage:

“ To a distinguished, had some suitor of equal caste should a father give his Daughter in accordance with the prescribed rule, though they have not attained age i.e., although she not have reached puberty”

Manu – IX – 88.

3. Widow- Remarriage:

“ But a widow, who from a wish to bear children slights her deceased husband by marrying again brings disgrace on herself here below and shall be excluded from the seat of her lord (in heaven)”

MANU: -V.161.

4. Divorce:

“The Husband is declared to be one with the wife which means that There could be no separation once a woman is married “

MANU:- IX.45.

5. Property:

: A wife, a son, and a slave, these three are declared to have no property, the wealth which they earn is (acquired) for him to whom they belong.”

MANU:- IX- 416.

Status of Women

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar who is considered as the emancipator of women observed that Hindu women were kept under men's control and they were not allowed in any field to have liberty as they should have enjoyed according to natural justice. Hereby Ambedkar explained the condition of the Hindu woman was as Manu can hardly be said to more tender to women than he was to the Shudra. Manu started with a low opinion of women. Manu Proclaimed:

“It is nature of women to reduce men in this (world); for that reason, the wife are never unguarded in (the company of) females “

MANU:- II.213

“ One should not sit in a lonely place with one's mother, sister or daughter, for the senses are powerful and master even a learned man.”

MANU:-II-215.

“Women do not care for beauty, nor is the attention fixed on age: (thinking); (it is enough that) he is a man; they give themselves to the handsome and to the ugly”

MANU:-IX.14.

“ Day and night women must be kept in dependence by the males of their (families) and if they attach themselves to sexual enjoyments, they must be kept under one's control”

MANU:- IX.2

“Her father protects (her) in child hood, her husband protects (her) in youth and her sons protect (her) in old age; a woman is never fit for Independence.”

MANU:- IX.3

Punishment

A wife, a son, a slave, a pupil a younger brother of the full blood, who have committed faults, may be beaten with a rope or a split bamboo’

-MANU: VIII.299

Ideal Life of the Woman

“Him to whom her father may give her or her brother with the father’s permission, she shall obey as long as he live and When he is dead, she must not insult his memory”

MANU:- V.151

B.R. Ambedkar opined that, in view of Manu, woman was a thing of no value. Rules existed before Manu only as a matter of social theory. Manu converted the social theory into the law of the state. Women were one of the Chief sections of the Aryan society which were flocking to join the religion of the Buddha and there by undermining the foundation of the Buddhas religion. Dr. Ambedkar finally affirmed that Manu wanted to stop the tide of women flowing in the direction of Buddhism.³

It is examined that in the later i.e., 9th century A.D. Sankarachary of Kerala proclaimed that “A woman is a sure gate of hell and she is poison in the disguise of nectar”. The Gupta dynasty which was considered a golden period in the history proved worst period for women, because in this period, Brahmanical Rules and dogmas, codified against women and were strictly enforced them. The lower caste unmarried girls were made in temples as ‘Devadasis’ for service including equal abuse by the priest in the name of god. The Ramayana, holy scripture of Hindus says that “No body can be as vile as a woman, who for a moment’s enjoyment does not understand the pains of hundred of births” (Aranyakanda Sloka 9), “A woman is impure from her birth” (Aranyakanda, Sloka 5), and even Muslim religion advocates strict rules for women to remain in Parda (Veil).⁴

2. Efforts for Social Status of Women

Women, in the Buddha’s times and preaching’s, had experienced a state of equality with men. Buddha, with his preaching’s and actions, identified women are as human beings and had equal status with men in respects of types of life. He recognized the character of human being, not caste. Buddha taught about upliftment of women from child hood to women hood from the cruel clutches of men. The sufferers in the Hindu society and the men and women of lower ranks were more attracted towards Buddhism and the Sangha would work on the principle of liberty, equality and fraternity. In Buddha’s times Economic equality was given to women without showing any discrimination on the lines of caste, race, sex in the Sangha. The exploitation in any form, anywhere, any range would not be tolerated in the Sangha,⁵ that was the status women enjoyed in the Buddha’s period.

The Buddha gave more importance to girl child and permitted them to enter into the Sangha, He stated:

“A women child.... May prove even a better off spring than a male. For she may grow up wise and virtuous, her husband’s mother reverencing True life; a daughter. The boy that she may bear may do great deeds and rule great realms, yea such a son of a noble wife become his country’s guide”⁶

Buddha eulogized that

“Woman is the commodity supreme because (as the commentator adds) she is of indispensable utility, or because through her Bodhisattvas and World rulers take birth”⁷

Buddha’s teachings reflected in B.R. Ambedkar to suggest that would get uplift themselves through education:

“Send your children to School education is necessity for females as it is for males. If you know how to read and write, there would be much progress. As you are so your children will be. Mould their lives in a virtuous way, for some should be such as would make a mark in this world”⁸

So Gautama Buddha was the first and real emancipator for the women’s life. B.R. Ambedkar, as the student of Buddha advocated that, if we want an egalitarian society, we must have equal social relations between man and woman. He said man should not dominate woman and woman deed to be subordinate man. The equality of woman with her opposite sex lies in the together living in marriage, Ambedkar, eulogized the importance of marriage which should give equal status to woman he said:

“Marriage is liability, you should not impose it upon your children. Unless they are financially able to meet the liabilities arising from marriage. Those who will marry will have to keep in mind that to have to many children is a crime. The parental duty lies in giving each child a better start than its parents had. Above all let every girl who marries stand by her husband, claim to be her husband’s friend and equal, and refuge to be his slave”⁹

The Hindu Code Bill

It is well known that social reform movement in India began to throw light on the problem of woman and made efforts towards the upliftment of the women. Ambedkar redrafted the bill, which was to be passed as a whole not as a piece meal legislation. The Hindu code bill contained the following issues 1) marriage 2) Divorce 3) Women’s right to property 4) adoption 5) Maintenance 6) Minority and guardianship and 7) succession to the different heirs to the property of a deceased dying intestate¹⁰. Ambedkar made several efforts towards women’s emancipation through the Hindu code bill in the constituent Assembly regarding necessity changing course of Hindu society Ambedkar said:

“Those who want to conserve must be ready to repair and all / want is that if you want to maintain the Hindu system, the Hindu culture, the Hindu society, do not hesitate to repair, where it is necessary.

The bill asks for nothing more than repairing those parts of the Hindu society which have almost become dilapidated”¹¹

After introducing the Bill, Ambedkar tried to defend the Bill and to get it passed, but the bill was not passed, because Nehru the Prime Minister of India, did not cooperate with Ambedkar, even Dr. Rajendra Prasad, the then President of India, said that if the bill passed, I shall resign. So from outside and inside of the Parliament, Dr. Ambedkar could not get support, finally the Bill was defeated and the spirit of the bill was killed.

3. Fundamental Rights in the Constitution

The fundamental rights in our constitution are meant for the individual progress. By having the fundamental rights, women would get social and economic justice.

- Article 14, gives equal status to women with men as all are equal before the law
- Article 15 gives special protection to women as affirmative action (as reservation or compensatory discrimination),
- Article 16 guarantees women to employment to get economic stability based on their educational qualification.
- Article 17, abolishes the practices of untouchability, amongst the dalit women with this, dalit women will get social mobility with the caste Hindus, and
- Article 21 gives the right to life irrespective of caste, class, race language and region. These fundamental rights, surely, ventilate the grievances of women from the time immemorial. By these rights women could obtain their lost social status in India.¹²
- Article 45. State Should Provide The Free And Compulsory Education To All The Children Up To Age Of 14 Years.^{12A}

4. Efforts of Jyoti Rao Phule and Savihri Bai Phule

Mahatma Jyoti Rao Phule, the father of Indian social revolution, was fore runner of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar as far as education of the down trodden and emancipation of women are concerned. Dr. Ambedkar accepted Phule as his 'guru' (MASTER) because he was for education. Mahatma Phule was one of the prominent social reformers and as such social reform was his main aim. He considered that education was just a sub-system of the whole system, but a foundation and a powerful tool for social revolution. He wanted education for not a selected a few but for all. That is the Mahatma Phule advocated about the importance of education.¹³

Savitri Bai Phule, wife of Jyoti Rao Phule worked with Jyoiba Phule teaching education to weaker sections and the untouchable girls, she was the first female teacher in entire Indian history to teach female education with the help of a Muslim friend Shri Us Man Sheik and his sister Fatima. Savitribai Phule while teaching had to bear the abuses, throwing of bricks of cow dung as she was busy in spreading girls education.¹⁴⁷

It is observed that the position of Indian woman is getting better than previous position, women confidently could find their representation to improve in social economic, political sectors of the country but, the improved position of women is not equal with men is right. They should continue their fight to get justice on par with men. In agriculture, industrial sector, women are not getting that due share.

5. Political Power of Women in Contemporary India

To improve their status, women collectively, and with committed spirit should fight to get their due share in political representation. Today, in India political power is the master key to open all locks as Ambedkar advocated. Women are half of the total population in India. But in political field, they are representing on 12% of total representation, so they should fight for their law making power. So far India had experienced with conducting 16 general elections to the Parliament from 1952-1914, and more than 350 elections were conducted in the state legislatures. In State Legislature also, women do not have their due representation

Political participation of women in Lok Sabha

S. No.	Year	Total Representatives	Men (in figure)	Women (in figure)
1	1952	489	469	22
2	1957	403	381	22
3	1962	494	463	31
4	1967	520	491	29
5	1971	518	489	29
6	1977	542	523	19
7	1980	529	501	28
8	1984	514	472	42
9	1989	529	500	29
10	1991	521	484	37
11	1996	543	503	40
12	1998	543	500	43
13	1999	543	494	49
14	2004	543	498	45
15	2009	543	484	59
16	2014	543	482	61
	Total	7828	7765	563
	Average	522	483	37

Source : Election Commission of India, Govt.of India. ; from 1951-2014

The above Table shows that though women are half of the Indian population, they are being given mere representation by their opposite sex. Since 1996 the 33% of women reservation bill of law making bodies has been in pending, it is not being passed by the Parliament, because the parliament is dominated by their male counterparts. Women in this regards should get unite against the injustice done by the men and they take their own movement until they achieve the 50% political representation because they are half of the population. They should get support from the likeminded political parties and leaders and N.G.O.s and their support to get their due share in political representation.

6. Women and Education

Many society education plays an important role to get development of the individuals and as whole of the nation. The position of women in Ancient and medieval periods was very low due to lack of education. To know the better position of women, we should observe the education and literacy status of women from 1901 to present day as follows:

Women Literacy Rate

S. No.	Census year	Total (%)	Male (%)	Female (%)
1	1901	5.35	9.83	0.60
2	1911	5.92	10.56	1.05
3	1921	7.16	12.21	1.81
4	1931	9.50	15.59	2.93
5	1941	16.10	24.90	7.30
6	1951	16.67	24.95	9.45
7	1961	24.02	34.44	12.95
8	1971	29.45	39.45	18.69
9	1981	36.23	46.89	24.82
10	1991	42.84	52.74	32.17
11	2001	64.83	75.26	53.67
12	2011	74.04	82.14	65.46

Source: Census of India, Crude literacy rate in India from 1901 to 2014.

It is observed that due to various effort of CENTRAL GOVERNMENT and STATE GOVERNMENT policies and schemes and with the cooperation of the Non-Governmental organizations, the educational Condition of women has improved. 2011 census says women literacy rate now stood at 65.46%, that means still there 34.54% of women in India are illiterates. This condition should be changed by the Central Government and State Governments. Women, themselves should collectively work for the better of women literacy. When women get cent per cent education then only they will be to understand the real life which is qualitative one.

7. Women Representation in Civil Services**Men and Women in UPSC, 2014**

Women in top 25 selected condition			Women in Total selections		
Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
15(60)	10(40)	25(100)	861(76.7)	261(23.3)	1122(100)

Source : Hindustan times, P.5, June 13, 2014

Women, now they entering in to every space of the human life, especially in Central services which are very essential to serve for the women community and they should develop the motto as B.R. Ambedkar said that self-help is the best to achieve their goals, if they depend on others they may not whole heartedly support for their cause. So Ambedkar said

‘tell the slave that he is a slave, he will revolt’

this should be their motivation.

8. Government’s Efforts for Women’s Status

Before independence, many social reformers made efforts for the improvement of women in India, like Raja Ram Mohan Roy, Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar and other leaders fought for the women’ cause. The British Government brought the Hindu Widow Remarriage Act, 1856. In the post independent India, Government made several laws to the upliftment of women: 15

1. the special marriage act of 1954,
2. the Hindu Succession Act and the Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956,
3. the Dowry Prohibition Act of 1961,
4. the maternity benefits act of 1961,
5. the Equal Remuneration Act of 1976,

6. the Criminal law Amendment Act of 1983

In the Globalization period and in the changed scenario government made number of acts for the women cause. In 2005, Indian Govt. brought the Domestic Violence Prohibition Act, this is a good law made for women, in 1996 the Supreme Court of India gave the guidelines to working organizations to protect women working in the same organizations. In 2013, Indian Government brought the Nirbhaya Act, to give protection from the crimes like rape and murder.

Many state governments are making the required laws for the upliftment of women and they are being implemented for the women cause. Andhra Pradesh state gives 30% opportunities in education and employment, like that Bihar, Gujarat, Rajasthan and many other states implementing the 50% of political representation in the local bodies.

9. Women their Efforts to Get Social Status

Today's Women's quest for equality with men has become universal. It gave birth to women's movement and feminist activities and associations. All over the world, feminism has its origin in social life and social structure. In recent years, the middle class women have taken up the issue of price rise and have launched anti-price movements in various parts of India. Within the household, women demanded equality with men. This demand is prevails anywhere in India and abroad. One thing is correctly observed that though women have hardly opportunities but they should adopt an independent path for their betterment. It is observed that in the present patriarchal society, they should have their demand as equality in aspects of life with men¹⁶. As Aristotle said inequality is the cause of revolutions in the universe. So to remove the existing inequality of women, they collectively should fight for their status which they demanding for now.

Today women first they should get education of all kinds for their upliftment, it is their main aim. Women should think of their due share in political representation, if they are able to get power, they will make laws for themselves. They should get equal share in the family and society in economic activities. Every work of them must be identified and recognized. The Feminist, now is on its heights, they should continue and at any cost they should continue it. As B.R. Ambedkar said that self-help is the best help, they need not depend on others now a days. First they remove their psychological feeling that woman is inferior, subordinate, weaker than man. If an body is given the right opportunities, he/she definitely achieve the desired goals.

Today, in India 137 crores of population with women as half of the total, until women get their sustainable development with men, society will not be in progress.

Gautama Buddha said that nothing is permanent, everything is subject to change, if there is no change, there will be no development. So in India women should get development, that should be the real change, that change for women's emancipation.

Inspite of the effort of the governments and women individual and collectively and achieved the present position, there must be further research for the real Emancipation of women in all aspects of life, then only women could get real SOCIAL STATUS IN INDIA and at abroad.

References

1. Bharathi, T. Abedkar and uplift of women, in Ambedkar and social justice, volume-II publication Division, Govt. of India, 1992, pp.264-265.
2. Sharma K.L., Indian Society, NCERT, New Delhi, 1992 pp. 124-125.
3. Ramesh Babu, Vipparla, the Social Philosophy of B.R. Ambedkar with special reference to womens emancipation (Ph.D. Thesis, not published), Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, 2006, p.84.
4. Deoraj Singh Dr. Ambedkar's thoughts on women's empowerment, in Dr. B.R. Ambedkar and social Transformation edited by Dr. Anjna Malhotra, Regal Publications, New Delhi, 2017, p.66.

5. B.R. Ambedkar Buddha and his Dhamma, Siddhartha College, Publications Bombay, 1957, p.415- 447.
6. Ibid, p.376
7. B.R. Ambedkar, Rise and fall of Hindu woman, Bheem patrika publications, Jalandhar, 1988, p.16.
8. Keer, Dhananjay, Dr. Ambedkar Life and Mission popular Prakashan, Bombay, 1977, p.104.
9. Ibid, p.352
10. Babasaheb Ambedkar writings and speeches, vol.XIV, part.1, p.5
11. A. Hari Prasanna; Ambedkar and the upliftment of the status of women, in Ambedkar and social justice, vol.I, publication Division Ministry & information and broadcasting government of India, New Delhi, 1992, p.119
12. Part III, Fundamental Rights, Indian Constitution. 12A. PART IV. of the Constitution of india
13. Gupta, N.L., Mahatma Phule An Educational Philosopher, Anmol Publications Pvt. Ltd., . Delhi, Pp.Vii-Viii
14. IBID.P.48.
15. Sharma K.L., Indian Society, NCERT, New Delhi, 1992 pp. 127
16. ibid. p.127.